

APPLICATION OF A VIRTUAL SHEAR STRESS MODEL AND COMPARISON WITH WWFE-III PREDICTIONS TO DESCRIBE THE NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Siegfried Galkin¹, Fabian Johannes Schirmaier¹ and Luise Kärger¹

¹Institute of Vehicle System Technology (FAST), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
Rintheimer Querallee 2, DE-76131 Karlsruhe, Germany
Email: siegfried.galkin@kit.edu, web page: <http://www.fast.kit.edu/lbt/index.php>

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ABSTRACT

To properly optimize CFRP composite structures under complex 3-D stress states, the nonlinear shear deformation behavior needs to be considered. For shear stresses which are much higher than the transverse normal stress, a linear elastic behavior can only be assumed up to 30% of the shear strength. Consequently, to achieve a global optimum for a CFRP structure, a material model must be used which is capable to reliably and efficiently predict the nonlinearity for shear stress-strain relations. Many computational models have been investigated in the past, which use the real stress states to calculate the current damage state of the shear modulus. Depending on the time increment, these approaches require several iterations at each time integration point to reach convergence.

In the presented approach a virtual stress state is applied which allows to calculate the current damage state of the shear modulus under combined shear-tension loading without iteration at the integration point. This approach is independent of the time increment of the FE solver to achieve an accurate damage state without any predefined tolerance value for convergence. To adjust the model, the main mechanical properties like moduli, strengths and Poisson's ratio are needed. Additionally, the threshold shear stress value, which denotes the beginning of the nonlinear behavior, and the failure shear strain need to be specified. Furthermore, the damage evolution from the beginning of the nonlinearity to the failure of the lamina is parameterized for pure shear. Based on the experimental test data of five different materials in the World Wide Failure Exercise III (WWFE-III) [1], the presented model is extrapolated for different stress ratios using a simple linear function method to compute the damage state depending on the stress ratio. The resulting failure shear strain and failure shear stresses are compared to results from different models of the WWFE-III Part A [2].

1 INTRODUCTION

New materials like FRPs have a very high lightweight potential in comparison to metals. While the mechanical behavior of metals is widely known, the anisotropic deformation and damage behavior of FRPs is still challenging to be reliably modelled. One aspect of this complex behavior is the non-linear shear stress behavior, which is not negligible since the optimal potential of FRPs is then limited. In most available FE tools the shear stress is considered as linear elastic. New approaches allow to use a predefined shear strain stress curve to model the non-linear behavior. If shear stress is superimposed with transverse tension, the maximum shear strain is highly affected by the current transverse stress. This superposition cannot be considered by predefined strain stress curves of pure shear tests. In recent publications many approaches to consider the non-linear behavior due to shear stress were published [3 - 6]. Although these approaches show good agreement with experimental results they either are analytical functions, not considering the effect of superimposed transverse tension, or have a lack in efficiency regarding iterations at each integration point that are needed to achieve convergence.

In this work a new approach is applied, which considers the effect of transverse tension and introduces a closed form solution for FRPs by using virtual stress states. The results of the approach are compared with the predictions of the WWFE-III [2].

2 MODELING SHEAR STRESS INDUCED MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR

If pure shear stress is applied to FRPs, linear elastic behavior occurs only at the beginning. After a certain shear stress (= threshold shear stress), the deformation behavior becomes non-linear. This start of nonlinearity is difficult to determine. The given experimental data in [1] have a range of the threshold shear stress from 6% to 42% of the shear strength. In the non-linear deformation range, the matrix is damaged by remaining defects on microscopic level. Therefore, if the composite is loaded periodically, the initial shear modulus will drop to a lower value after unloading. To consider the non-linearity of the composite, the threshold shear stress must be known. It can be determined from experiments or assumed from a micro-damage evolution model. If in addition to shear also transverse tension is applied, the micro-damage evolution is suppressed although macro damage may occur earlier. This effect depends on the current stress ratio and needs to be considered, if the actual damage state of a FRP shall be calculated.

Puck and Manningel [5] propose a damage evolution function which connects the current damage state with the current stress exposure. The function for pure shear stress can be simplified to the following expression:

$$d(f_E) = d_{\max} \left(\frac{f_E - f_E^{thr}}{1 - f_E^{thr}} \right)^n, \quad (1)$$

where f_E is the stress exposure to define inter-fiber-fracture (IFF), f_E^{thr} is the stress exposure at the threshold shear stress for a pure shear stress load, d_{\max} the value of the damage variable for pure shear at IFF and n is a fitting parameter. With this damage-evolution function, the threshold shear stress can be calculated, if the value cannot be clearly identified in experiments. This function fits well with the FRP material used in [5]. Also for experimental data given in [1] a good agreement can be found for AS4/3501-6 and E-glass/epoxy. For IM7/8552 and G40-800/5260 a difference of about 5% to the actual shear stress is calculated. For superimposed transverse tension, Puck and Manningel [5] introduce a scaling factor $C^{(\sigma_{22})}$, which needs to be fitted to all strain-stress curves (with stress ratios greater than zero) to comply with the following expression:

$$d(f_E) = d_{\max} \left(\frac{f_E^{(\tau_{12})} + C^{(\sigma_{22})} (f_E - f_E^{(\tau_{12})}) - f_E^{thr}}{1 - f_E^{thr}} \right)^n, \quad (2)$$

where $f_E^{(\tau_{12})}$ is calculated by using the actual shear stress. The results presented in [5] correlate well with experimental results. If the shear stress becomes very small, $f_E^{(\tau_{12})}$ tends to zero. Therefore the scaling factor leads to a damage state value for shear stress at IFF which is always higher than zero, even when the actual shear stress is very small, see Figure 1. Since the damage state proposed in [5] depends on the current shear stress, it can only be solved iteratively, which makes it computationally very expensive. To circumvent an iterative algorithm at each time integration point, a closed form solution is needed.

3 MODELING NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOR USING VIRTUAL STRESS STATES

To avoid iterations at the integration point and still have a reliable closed form solution for micro damage evolution, a virtual stress state is introduced in [7] and applied in this work. This approach is based on a linear function between the damage state and the stress ratio. The linear function is determined from experimental results. Using this linear correlation, the whole micro-damage evolution spectrum can be generated by only using the threshold shear stress as one specific composite parameter. To generate this spectrum, the Puck failure criterion for mode A is used [8]. The different damage evolutions of the whole spectrum are visualized in Figure 2. As explained for the damage evolution in chapter 2, the approach in [7] also depends on the current shear stress, which would still require iterations. Therefore, a closed form solution is defined, which utilizes the assumed linear correlation between damage state and stress ratio.

Figure 1: Damage evolution for different stress ratios for the approach of Puck and Manningel [5]

Figure 2: Damage evolution for different stress ratios using the approach from Galkin et al. [7]

In [7], a closed form solution is developed based on so-called virtual stress states. The virtual stress state is defined by the applied virtual shear stress and the real transverse tension stress. For the virtual stress states, a failure envelope can be calculated, which is defined by the virtual stress exposure and is similar to the IFF failure envelope function from Puck for mode A [8]. To calculate the failure envelope, the initial linear elastic shear modulus, the shear strength, the threshold shear stress (which denotes the start of the non-linear behavior) and the failure shear strain for pure shear are needed. Additionally, the damage evolution of pure shear stress is needed to derive the damage evolution of each stress ratio, before macroscopic failure occurs. When all parameters of the damage evolution function are determined, the current damage state can be calculated directly from the current virtual stress exposure, which is based on the current virtual stress state and on the damage evolution function at pure shear stress.

4 APPLICATION OF THE APPROACH USING VIRTUAL STRESS STATES

In the following, the approach presented in [7] is compared with the results predicted by the participants of the WWFE-III [1] for test case 1. In test case 1, a transverse tension of 14 MPa is applied to a UD-laminate and afterwards a shear load on the 1-2-plane is applied. The used material is a carbon fiber prepreg AS4/3501-6. The data needed to define the micro-damage evolution model are summarized in Table 1.

Material data		Measured data	Virtual data used
$R_{\parallel\perp}$	[MPa]	79	133.3
R_{\perp}	[MPa]	48	48
τ_{12}^{thr}	[MPa]	7.37	7.37
γ_{12}^B	[-]	0.02	0.02
G_{12}^{init}	[GPa]	6.667	6.667

Table 1: Essential material data to parametrize the used approach

The results of the different approaches applied to test case 1 differ in maximum shear stress and maximum shear strain. Since the shear strength of AS4/3501-6 is 79 MPa, the results of the test case need to be lower than the shear strength. All participants fulfill this condition. The maximum shear strain for the test case 1 should also be lower than the maximum shear strain of 2 % at pure shear load. However, the maximum shear strain is only in the predictions of three participants lower than 2 %.

Figure 3: Comparison of the predicted shear stress results for WWFE-III test case 1

Figure 4: Comparison of the predicted shear strain results for WWFE-III test case 1

In comparison to the predicted results of WWFE-III, the current approach is similar to the prediction of Flatscher et al. [9] in terms of maximum shear stress. Both models use the same failure criterion from Puck. The maximum shear strain, however, is slightly different. The results are summarized in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Experimental results are, unfortunately, not available.

The results of the two approaches presented in chapter 3 are almost equal. The main difference is that the approach using virtual stress states (“Galkin VST”) is computationally more efficient than the approach which only assumes the linear correlation between damage variable and stress ratio without using virtual stresses (“Galkin”). The predicted shear stress of the VST approach differs only by 0.2 MPa. The maximum shear strain of 1.52% is equal in both approaches. Compared to the predictions of the participants of the WWFE-III, the computed maximum shear strains are close to the predictions of Carrere et al. [10], Pinho et al. [11] and Pettermann et al. [9]. The computed maximum shear stresses are similar for all approaches.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Considering the micro-damage evolution of FRPs due to shear stress with superimposed transverse tension is necessary to achieve the global optimum for a FRP structure. Many micro-damage evolution theories have been published. Although the results of many publications fit well with experimental results, the main disadvantage is the efficiency of the calculation. The reason for the high computational effort is the dependence of the damage state from the current stress state. Therefore, the damage evolution equations have to be solved iteratively. In the present work, a closed form solution is applied, which works without iterations. A detailed description of the approach can be found in [7]. The results of the closed form solution correlate well with the predictions of the participants of the WWFE-III.

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